

NATURAL FLAVONES. PART IV. ON THE CONSTITUTION OF ERIANTHIN, THE YELLOW COLOURING MATTER OF *BLUMEA ERIANTHA* DC.

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Erianthin, the yellow colouring matter of *Blumea eriantha* DC., has been shown to be 5 :7-dihydroxy-3 :6 :8 :3' :4'-pentamethoxyflavone.

Blumea eriantha DC (N. O. *Compositae*), a native of Western India, has only a restricted use in Indian medicine. A warm infusion of the plant is given as a sudorific in catarrhal affections. It is also considered to be diuretic and emmenagogue. Dymock, Warden and Hooper (*Pharmacographia Indica*, Vol. II, p. 254) reported the presence of the following constituents in the plant : chlorophyll, a dark acid resin, tannin (trace), a volatile oil, a wax and a crystalline, yellow, nitrogen-free compound, m.p. 156°. The colour reactions and the behaviour of the last compound towards acids and alkali were also recorded by them.

The essential oil of *B. eriantha* has been the subject of a recent investigation (Schimmel's Report, 1937, p. 8 ; cf. also Amin and Patel, *Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1936, p. 200). It contains 95% ketones, the chief constituent of which is *d*-carvotanacetone.

The present communication deals with the isolation and examination of the colouring matter mentioned above. By the method described in the Experimental we have been able to obtain it in a yield not exceeding 0.03%. The crude substance melted at 154°, but on careful purification the m.p. rose to 161°. The properties of this compound agreed with those of Dymock's colouring matter. We propose the name 'Erianthin' for this substance, which appears to be a new natural product. Erianthin forms yellow transparent prisms or needles which dissolve in alcoholic potassium hydroxide, or concentrated hydrochloric acid with a deep yellow colour. It is insoluble in 0.5% aqueous alkali, liquor ammonia or dilute mineral acids. It dissolves, however, in 5% aqueous alkali, and the alkaline solution is stable to aerial oxidation. Ferric chloride imparts an olive-green colour to an alcoholic solution of erianthin, but ferrous sulphate does not produce any characteristic colour. Treated with magnesium and hydrochloric acid, alcoholic erianthin produces a pink colour. Apparently it behaves like a hydroxyflavone.

The analytical data of erianthin are in agreement with the formula $C_{14}H_3O_2(OMe)_5(OH)_2$ and it is further supported by the formation of a colourless diacetyl derivative. Hydrolytic fission of erianthin by means of alkali produced an acid, m.p. 177.5° , which was definitely identified as veratric acid. The partial formula of erianthin may, therefore, be represented by (I).

We have now to allocate positions to the two OH and three OMe groups in the benzopyrone nucleus, which can have a maximum of five substituents. The stability of an alkaline solution of erianthin in air excludes the possibility of existence of a free OH group in position 3. Both the phenolic groups consequently must be present in the benzene nucleus. On the basis of the hypothesis, put forward by Bose and Nath in Part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **15**, 141), that in natural polyhydroxyflavones or their partially methylated products, a free OH group is always to be found in position 5, the formula (I) may further be expanded to (II). Methylation of erianthin by means of diazomethane led to a crystalline yellow monomethyl derivative. Prolonged contact with the reagent failed to give the dimethyl derivative. Monomethylerianthin gave a green ferric test and a colourless acetyl derivative. These observations may be accepted as an additional evidence of the presence of an OH group in position 5, since the OH group in this particular position is known to resist methylation by diazomethane (*cf.* Robinson and Tseng, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1004).

The second OH group must occupy the *meta*-position with regard to the first, because erianthin gives negative tests with alkaline *o*-dinitrobenzene

(Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Sir P. C. Ray 70th Birthday Vol., 1933, 65) as also with chloropentammine cobaltichloride (Shibata and Hattori, *Acta Phytochim.*, 1930, 8, 117). The three remaining positions, namely 3, 6 and 8, must consequently be occupied by the three methoxy groups. In other words, erianthin should be regarded as 5:7-dihydroxy-3:6:8:3':4'-penta-methoxyflavone (III), and monomethylerianthin as (IV).

The isolation of a compound of the type (III) from natural sources is of interest because it happens to be the second known natural product of the heptahydroxyflavone series, the first being gardenin from *Gardenia lucida* (Bose and Nath, *loc. cit.*). Incidentally it might be mentioned that erianthin is one of the few known derivatives of pentahydroxybenzene, occurring in nature.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of Erianthin.—A supply of *Blumea eriantha* DC., in flower, was obtained from the Bombay Presidency through the kindness of Mr. S. N. Bal, M.Sc., Ph.C., Officer-in-Charge, Botanical Survey of India and Mr. L. S. S. Kumar, Economic Botanist to the Government of Bombay, to whom we offer our best thanks. The air-dried plant (1 kg.) was cut into small pieces and percolated with commercial methyl alcohol during 60 hours. The deep green extract was concentrated to about 900 c.c. and treated while still hot with concentrated aqueous lead acetate (15 c.c.). The precipitate was filtered off and the filtrate freed from lead by means of hydrogen sulphide. The filtrate was concentrated to about 200 c.c. in vacuum and allowed to stand in a cold chamber (0°) for 72 hours. Crude erianthin separated out along with much tarry matter, which was removed by washing with cold alcohol. The mother-liquor and washings gave a second crop of crystals on being kept for about a week in the cold.

The crude erianthin melted at 154°. Repeated crystallisations from chloroform-alcohol and acetone gave yellow transparent prisms, m.p. 161°. Further crystallisations did not improve the m.p. Erianthin was obtained in yields varying from 0.02 to 0.03 %. It is insoluble in petroleum ether, sparingly soluble in alcohol, ether and benzene, moderately soluble in acetone and acetic acid and freely soluble in chloroform. (Found in samples dried at 110° in *vacuo* over P₂O₅: C, 59.4; H, 4.94; OMe, 38.54. C₂₀H₂₀O₆ requires C, 59.41; H, 4.95; 5 OMe, 38.36 per cent).

Stability of Alkaline Erianthin in Air.—Through a solution of erianthin in 5% potassium hydroxide a rapid current of air was passed for 1.5 hours. The colour of the solution did not change. On acidification with hydrochloric acid a pale yellow crystalline precipitate was obtained, which melted

at 160.5° after crystallisation from acetone, and which did not depress the m.p. of pure erianthin.

Diacetylerianthin.—A mixture of erianthin (0.1 g.), acetic anhydride (2 c.c.) and a drop of pyridine was gently boiled for 3 hours. The liquid products from the reaction mixture were removed under reduced pressure and the crystalline residue was taken up with benzene, charcoaled, and filtered. The filtrate on concentration and dilution with petroleum ether gave colourless needles. Twice recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, the acetyl derivative melted at 163°. (Found in sample dried at 110° in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ : OMe, 32.00. C₂₄H₂₄O₁₁ requires 5 OMe, 31.8 per cent). It gave no ferric test in alcohol.

Hydrolysis of Erianthin.—Erianthin (0.4 g.) was heated under reflux for 12 hours with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (15 c.c. of 20%). The product was evaporated to dryness, the residue taken up with water and extracted with ether. The ether extract gave a small quantity of red tarry matter, which could not be crystallised. The aqueous portion, on concentration and acidification with hydrochloric acid, gave a crystalline precipitate. This was collected, washed with cold water and purified by sublimation in high vacuum and by subsequent crystallisation from dilute methyl alcohol. The colourless prisms melted at 177.5° and did not depress the m.p. of an authentic specimen of veratric acid, m.p. 177.5-78°. (Found in sample dried at 110° in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ : OMe, 33.3. Calc. for C₉H₁₀O₄ : 2 OMe, 34.06 percent).

Monmethylerianthin (IV).—Erianthin (0.2 g.), dissolved in pure methyl alcohol, was treated with an excess of ethereal diazomethane and the mixture left overnight at room temperature. The residue left after removal of the solvents was distilled at 210-30°/0.02 mm., the yellow distillate was twice crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol as pale yellow needles, m.p. 141°. (Found in sample dried at 100° in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ : OMe, 44.6. C₂₁H₂₂O₉ requires 6 OMe, 44.5 per cent). It gave a green colour with ferric chloride in alcohol.

Monomethylmonoacetylerianthin.—The foregoing compound (0.08 g.) was acetylated and the product purified in the manner indicated under diacetylerianthin. The acetyl derivative formed colourless needles, m.p. 131°. It showed no ferric test in alcohol. (Found in sample dried at 100° in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ : OMe, 40.8. C₂₃H₂₄O₁₀ requires 6 OMe, 40.42 per cent).

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